

A New Excellent Diastereoselective Synthesis of β -Coumarinylacrylates Using the Wittig and Wittig-Horner Reagents : Salient Features of Their Stereochemistry and Preferred Conformation[†]

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β -Coumarinyl acrylates were prepared in excellent diastereomeric excess from formylcoumarins applying the Wittig and Wittig-Horner reactions.

Recently we could successfully undertake a series of systematic studies on the various selectivities of grignards as well as bromozinc enolates applying formylcoumarins¹ and coumarinyl methyl ketones^{2,3} as the substrates in order to develop an effective methodology for the synthesis of diverse types of naturally occurring coumarins⁴. It is further interesting to record that the applications of the well-known Wittig⁵ and Wittig-Horner⁶ reactions are very much restricted in the elaboration of varieties of natural and unnatural coumarin systems^{7,8}. In the present investigation we have carried out successfully the synthesis of some new β -coumarinylacrylic esters exploiting both the Wittig and Wittig-Horner reactions. The excellent diastereoselectivity as well as chemoselectivity recorded during this new synthesis of β -coumarinylacrylates along with their stereochemical and conformational assignments constitutes the subject-matter of the present communication.

4-Formylcoumarin (1) and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (2) selected for this purpose were prepared¹ through selenium dioxide oxidation of the respective methylcoumarins. The Wittig reaction was performed in refluxing benzene under anhydrous condition using triphenylphosphonium ethoxy-

1 R = CHO, R¹ = H2 R = CHO, R¹ = OMe3 R = CH = ^ECHCO₂Et, R¹ = H4 R = CH = ^ECHCO₂Et, R¹ = OMe5 R = CH = ^ECMeCO₂Et, R¹ = H6 R = CH = ^ECMeCO₂Et, R¹ = OMePh₃P = CRCO₂Et

7 R = H

8 R = Me

(EtO)₂P = ⁺CRCO₂Et

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O⁻

9 R = H

10 R = Me

carbonylmethylide (7) and ethoxycarbonylmethylmethylide (8). Usual workup followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded in excellent yield the respective Wittig products which could be unequivocally established as ethyl β -coumarinylacrylates (3,4) and ethyl β -coumarinyl- α -methylacrylates (5,6). The configuration of the olefinic double bond located at C-1' position in 3 and 4 could be readily established as *E* since the ³J value of about 17 Hz has been uniformly recorded for H-1' and H-2' signals in their respective ¹H nmr spectrum. The very formation of the single diastereomer *E* as the Wittig products 3 and 4 from the formylcoumarins 1 and 2 respectively, clearly demonstrates the excellent diastereoselectivity during the reaction of triphenylphosphonium ethoxycarbonylmethylide (7). It is gratifying to note that this excellent diastereoselectivity observed is not that much uncommon with stable ylides which as a rule add up to an aldehydic or ketocarbonyl functionality generating an intermediate betaine involving a perfectly reversible step⁹ which actually controls the stereochemistry of the product. It is highly interesting to note that an excellent chemoselectivity has also been recorded simultaneously as the α,β -unsaturated aldehyde and lactonecarbonyl moieties in 1 and 2 did not interfere at all during the formation of 3 and 4 in contrary to some of our previous observations¹⁻³.

Correct configurational assignment of 1',2' - double bond in 5 and 6 synthesised using carbethoxymethylmethyl-enetriphenylphosphorane (8) was taken up in order to assess the diastereoselectivity of the reactions. The unambiguous correct assignment of 1'-H, appeared as a quintet (*J* 1 Hz) at δ 7.65 and 7.61 in 5 and 6 respectively, could be achieved by detecting the cross peaks¹⁰ in the respective 2D COSY (¹H-¹H) spectrum with the signals for 2'-Me and 3-H. In fact all the ¹H nmr signals appeared for 5 and 6 could be unequivocally assigned by examining the various cross peaks appeared in the 2D COSY (¹H-¹H) spectra. This helped us to get a perfectly right entry point¹⁰ for performing NOE experiments¹¹ further on the Wittig products 5 and 6. It is

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday
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highly interesting to note that substantial NOE enhancements for the signals at 3-H and 5-H in both the acrylates **5** and **6** were observed on irradiating the 1'-H signal and vice versa. Moreover, definite NOE enhancement was also recorded for the 3-H and 5-H signals through the irradiation of the signals for 2'-Me and vice versa. All these observations unequivocally prove that 1'-H and 2'-Me in **5** as well as in **6** do not maintain a close proximity in space and should be strictly *anti* in their relationship from configurational standpoint. This fully corroborates the configuration of 1',2'-double bond in **5** and **6** as *E*. Hence the excellent diastereoselectivity along with chemoselectivity turns out to be perfectly true also for this ylide **8** during the Wittig reaction with **1** and **2**.

The above excellent diastereoselective and chemoselective properties of the ylides **7** and **8** in the Wittig reaction encouraged us to examine further the selectivity of closely analogous phosphonate carbanion¹² on the formylcoumarins. As a sequel the Wittig-Horner reaction was carried out on **2** in absolute ethanol at room temperature using the respective carbanions **9** and **10** of triethyl phosphonoacetate and phosphonopropionate. Normal workup followed by column chromatographic purification over silica gel finally afforded in very good yield the diastereomerically pure acrylic esters **4** and **6**. The very formation of **4** and **6** further suggests that both the Wittig reagents (**7,8**) and Wittig-Horner reagents (**9,10**) behave in similar way with formylcoumarins in recording excellent diastereoselectivity along with chemoselectivity.

The preferred conformation of acrylic ester side-chain with respect to coumarin moiety in **5** and **6** can also be logically deduced from the various observations of NOE experiments. Thus the NOE enhancements for 1'-H with 3-H and 5-H as well as for 2'-Me with 3-H and 5-H necessitate a rapid equilibrium between the preferred conformations **11** and **12** whose time of residence happens to be much shorter than nmr time-scale. The possibility of slow equilibration between the two conformers **11** and **12** has been ruled out¹³ due to the fact that rotation around single bonds is generally fast on the nmr time-scale particularly at room temperature. Fully in accordance with this idea all the signals of **5** and **6** appearing in their respective ¹H nmr spectrum turn out to be extremely sharp and well-defined through averaging over¹⁴ the conformations **11** and **12**.

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COU = 4-Coumarinyl/7-Methoxy-4-coumarinyl

Finally, the preferred conformation of α,β -unsaturated ester moiety present in the acrylic ester side-chain of **5** and **6** has been established to be *s-trans* (**13**) and not *s-cis* (**14**) since positive NOE enhancement has been observed between 1'-H and methylene as well as methyl groups of 2'-CO₂Et. Hence the preferred conformation of **5** as well as **6** may be convincingly represented by **15** and **16** which are in rapid equilibrium. It is further interesting to note that the 7-OMe group in **6** does not enjoy any preferred planar conformations with respect to aromatic σ -frame as NOE increment was observed in the intensity of the signals for 6-H and 8-H on irradiating 7-OMe demanding the close proximity of Me group in 7-OMe with respect to 6-H as well as 8-H.

16 R = H, OMe

At this juncture it is highly interesting to consider in a nutshell the results of our previous studies¹⁻³ on formylcoumarins and coumarinyl alkyl ketones. All these could establish the Reformatsky reagents as highly chemoselective in comparison to the Grignard reagents which failed to record such selectivity in any appreciable degree. From the present investigation on the synthesis of new coumarinylacrylates it turns out that the Wittig and Wittig-Horner reactions are far more superior to the Reformatsky reaction at least from the chemoselectivity standpoint. Further investigations in this attractive field are in progress in order to establish ultimately the Wittig and Wittig-Horner reactions as a highly effective methodology for the synthesis of diversified type natural as well as unnatural coumarins. Moreover, these new β -coumarinyl acrylates may serve as an effective synthon in the building up of a new class of 3,4-benzocoumarins⁴.

Experimental

All m.ps. reported are uncorrected. Uv spectra (aldehyde free ethanol) were recorded on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Hitachi 270-30 data processor, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃, using TMS as an internal standard) on a Bruker WH250 spectrometer which

was also engaged in NOE studies and 2D-homonuclear (^1H - ^1H) COSY experiments and mass spectra on Finnigan Mat 1020C spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

Wittig reaction with 4-formylcoumarin (1) and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (2) employing triphenylphosphonium ethoxycarbonylmethylide (7) and ethoxycarbonylmethylmethylide (8). General procedure: A mixture of the respective formylcoumarin 1 or 2 (2.9 mmol) and triphenyl-phosphonium ethoxycarbonylmethylide (7) or ethoxy-carbonylmethylmethylide (8) (2.9 mmol), prepared as reported in the literature^{15,16} from the respective phosphonium bromide, was refluxed in dry benzene (40 ml) under anhydrous condition for 12 h when no further progress of the reaction was indicated by monitoring with tlc. After keeping the mixture overnight it was initially washed with 1% aqueous sulphuric acid (6×15 ml) and finally with saturated aqueous brine solution (6×15 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and on evaporating out the solvent a solid mass left behind which on tlc revealed the presence of a new nonpolar product along with the respective starting material (1 or 2). The pure coumarinyl acrylates (3-6) were finally obtained by column chromatography over silica gel on eluting with 5 to 7% ether-petrol mixture.

Wittig-Horner reaction of 2 with the respective carbanions 9 and 10 of triethyl phosphonoacetate and phosphonopropionate. General procedure: A solution of sodium ethoxide in ethanol was prepared employing fine pieces of metallic sodium (2.4 mmol) and perfectly dry absolute alcohol (5 ml) and it was subsequently cooled. To it the respective triethyl phosphonoacetate or propionate (2.4 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring at 0° during 10 min following the literature procedure^{17,18} to get ultimately a clear solution of the corresponding anion of triethyl phosphonoacetate (9) or propionate (10). A solution of 7-methoxy-4-formylcoumarin (2; 2.4 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was added slowly to the solution of 9 or 10 under perfectly anhydrous condition at such a rate that the temperature of the reaction mixture did not exceed 20°. After complete addition of formylcoumarin (2), the reaction mixture was further stirred at room temperature for 2 h and finally kept overnight. It was subsequently poured into an excess of aqueous brine solution (150 ml) followed by extraction with ethyl acetate (3×40 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with saturated brine solution (3×20 ml), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated. The crude reaction product thus obtained was column chromatographed over silica gel to get ultimately the pure acrylic esters (4 and 6) as a relatively nonpolar product using 7% ether-petrol mixture as eluant.

Relevant experimental data and spectral characteristics of new β -coumarinylacrylates (3-6) are given below.

3 (76%), m.p. 70° (ether-petrol) (Found : C, 68.79; H, 4.86. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 68.85; H, 4.91%); λ_{max} 237 (log ϵ 4.24), 319 sh nm (3.82); ν_{max} 1736, 1716, 1636, 1602 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 1.38 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH_2Me), 4.31 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, OCH_2Me), 6.57 (1H, d, J 0.7 Hz, 3-H), 6.58 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 2'-H), 7.34 (1H, dt, J 1.5 and 8 Hz, 6-H), 7.40 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 8 Hz, 8-H), 7.58 (1H, dt, J 1.5 and 8 Hz, 7-H), 7.73 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 8 Hz, 5-H), 7.94 (1H, dd, J 16 and 0.7 Hz, 1'-H); ^{13}C nmr* δ 117.5 (t, C-3), 124.6 (t, C-5), 124.5 (t, C-6), 127.3 (t, C-7), 113.5 (t, C-8), 132.4 (t, C-1'), 136.6 (t, C-2'), 61.4 (s, C-5'), 14.2 (p, C-6'), *(q, C-2, C-4, C-4a, C-8a, C-3'); m/z 244 (23% M^{++}), 216 (4.5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}$), 199 (7, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-OEt}$), 171 (100, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et}$), 143 (4.5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO-CO}_2\text{Et}$), 115 (68, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-2CO-CO}_2\text{Et}$).

4 (72% Wittig, 65% Wittig-Horner), m.p. 102° (chloroform-petrol) (Found : C, 65.62; H, 5.06. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 65.6; H, 5.11%); λ_{max} 381 nm (log ϵ 3.73), 347.5 (3.93), 250 (4.27); ν_{max} 1742, 1712, 1642, 1614 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 1.36 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, OCH_2Me), 3.89 (3H, s, 7-OMe), 4.29 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, OCH_2Me), 6.34 (1H, d, J 0.7 Hz, 3-H), 6.50 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, 2'-H), 6.88 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.90 (1H, dd, J 2 and 8 Hz, 6-H), 7.54 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H), 7.83 (1H, dd, J 17 and 0.7 Hz, 1'-H); m/z 274 (51%, M^{++}), 246 (15, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}$), 229 (12, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-OEt}$), 201 (100, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et}$), 189 (9.5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-3CO-H}$), 173 (9.5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-CO}$), 145 (14.6, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-2CO}$), 130 (12, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-2CO-Me}$), 115 (7, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-2CO-CH}_2\text{O}$), 102 (26, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-3CO-Me}$).

5 (74%), m.p. 106° (chloroform-petrol) (Found : C, 69.83; H, 5.36. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 69.76; H, 5.42%); λ_{max} 279 nm (log ϵ 4.00), 236 (4.11), 320 sh (3.75); ν_{max} 1744, 1712, 1610 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 1.40 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH_2Me), 2.03 (3H, d, J 1 Hz, 2'-Me), 4.34 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, OCH_2Me), 6.32 (1H, d, J 1 Hz, 3-H), 7.30 (1H, dt, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz, 6-H), 7.39 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz, 8-H), 7.54 (1H, dt, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz, 7-H), 7.59 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz, 5-H), 7.65 (1H, quin, J 1 Hz, 1'-H); ^{13}C nmr δ 160.5 (q, C-2), 117.4 (t, C-3), 149.8 (q, C-4), 118.4 (q, C-4a), 125.5 (t, C-5), 124.5 (t, C-6), 131.2 (t, C-7), 115.2 (t, C-8), 153.9 (q, C-8a), 132.3 (t, C-1'), 135.8 (q, C-2'), 167.0 (q, C-3'), 61.5 (s, C-5'), 14.1 (p, C-6'), 14.5 (p, 2'-Me); m/z 258 (24%, M^{++}), 230 (5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}$), 213 (12, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-OEt}$), 202 (10, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-2CO}$), 185 (100, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et}$), 157 (17, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CO}_2\text{Et-CO}$), 145 (5, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-CH=CMCO}_2\text{Et}$), 129 (20, $\text{M}^{++}\text{-}$

*DEPT pulse sequence was applied in all ^{13}C nmr experiments to determine the nature of carbon signals (p/s/t/q).

**Quaternary carbons could not be detected unambiguously with full certainty.

$\dot{C}O_2Et-2CO$), 128 (50, $M^{++}-\dot{C}H=CMeCO_2Et-\dot{O}H$), 127 (24, $M^{++}-\dot{C}H=CMeCO_2Et-H_2O$), 102 (12, $M^{++}-\dot{C}H=CMeCO_2Et-C_2H_2-H_2O+\dot{H}$); 2D-COSY (1H - 1H) strong cross peaks for 1'-H with 2'-Me and 3-H, 2'-CO₂CH₂Me with 2'-CO₂CH₂Me and 5-H with 6-H; Homonuclear (1H - 1H) NOE increment in the intensity 25 and 27% of 5-H and 3-H on irradiating 1'-H, 14 and 24% of 2'-CO₂CH₂Me and 1'-H on irradiating 2'-CO₂CH₂Me, 26 and 23% of 3-H and 5-H on irradiating 2'-Me, 16 and 23% of 2'-Me and 1'-H on irradiating 3-H.

6 (67% Wittig, 68% Wittig-Horner), m.p. 122° (chloroform-petrol) (Found : C, 66.58; H, 5.61; C₁₆H₁₆O₅ calcd. for : C, 66.66; H, 5.55%); λ_{max} 381 nm (log ϵ 3.27), 341 (4.01), 331.5 (4.02), 278 (4.46); ν_{max} 1744, 1712, 1622, 1606 cm⁻¹; 1H nmr δ 1.38 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, OCH₂Me), 2.00 (3H, d, J 1 Hz, 2'-Me), 3.90 (3H, s, 7-OMe), 4.32 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, OCH₂Me), 6.14 (1H, d, J 1 Hz, 3-H), 6.85 (1H, dd, J 2.4 and 9.5 Hz, 6-H), 6.86 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.41 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, 5-H), 7.61 (1H, quin, J 1 Hz, 1'-H); ^{13}C nmr δ 161.1 (q, C-2), 112.6 (t, C-3), 149.9 (q, C-4), 111.9 (q, C-4a), 126.5 (t, C-5), 112.0 (t, C-6), 163.3 (q, C-7), 101.2 (t, C-8), 155.8 (q, C-8a), 131.6 (t, C-1'), 135.5 (q, C-2'), 167.1 (q, C-3'), 61.5 (s, C-5'), 14.1 (p, C-6'), 14.5 (p, 2'-Me), 55.8 (p, 7-OMe); m/z 288 (81%, M^{++}), 259 (26, $M^{++}-CO-\dot{H}$), 243 (16, $M^{++}-\dot{O}Et$), 231 (25, $M^{++}-CO-\dot{H}-C_2H_4$), 215 (100, $M^{++}-\dot{C}O_2Et$), 214 (18, $M^{++}-\dot{C}O_2Et-\dot{H}$), 187 (32, $M^{++}-\dot{C}O_2Et-CO$), 172 (17, $M^{++}-\dot{C}O_2Et-CO-Me$), 171 (10, $M^{++}-HCO_2Et-CO-Me$), 144 (18, $M^{++}-CH_2=CMeCO_2Et-CH_2O$), 127 (12, $M^{++}-CH_2=CMeCO_2Et-CH_2O-\dot{O}H$), 116 (18, $M^{++}-CH_2=CMeCO_2Et-CO-CH_2O$), 115 (37, $M^{++}-CH_2=CMeCO_2Et-CO-\dot{O}Me$); 2D-COSY (1H - 1H) : strong cross peaks for 1'-H with 2'-Me and 3-H, 5-H with 6-H, 2'-CO₂CH₂Me with 2'-CO₂CH₂Me and weak cross peaks for 7-OMe with 6-H and 8-H; Homonuclear (1H - 1H) NOE increment in the intensity 24, 26 and 15% of 3-H, 5-H and 2'-CO₂CH₂Me on irradiating 1'-H; 14 and 25% of 2'-CO₂CH₂Me and 1'-H on irradiating 2'-CO₂CH₂Me, 22 and 25% of 6-H and 8-H on irradiating 7-OMe, 16 and 27% of 2'-Me and 1'-H on irradiating 3-H, 24 and 21% of 3-H and 5-H on irradiating 2'-Me.

All yields were calculated on the basis of the recovery of the respective starting material. All the products furnished

satisfactory C and H analyses along with uv, ir, 1H and ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral data, fully consistent with their respective structures proposed.

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